

Differential rewarding effect of electrical stimulation of the lateral hypothalamus and parabrachial complex: functional characterization and the relevance of opioid systems and dopamine

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Please list at least 3 keywords which relate to your manuscript::	Reward, lateral hypothalamus (LH), external lateral parabrachial nucleus (LPBe), opioids, dopamine
Abstract:	<p>Background: Since the discovery of rewarding intracranial self-stimulation by Olds and Milner, extensive data have been published on the biological basis of reward. Although participation of the mesolimbic dopaminergic system is well documented, its precise role has not been fully elucidated, and some authors have proposed the involvement of other neural systems in processing specific aspects of reinforced behavior.</p> <p>Aims and methods: We reviewed published data, including our own findings, on the rewarding effects induced by electrical stimulation of the lateral hypothalamus (LH) and of the external lateral parabrachial area (LPBe) -a brainstem region involved in processing the rewarding properties of natural and artificial substances-, and compared its functional characteristics as observed in operant and non-operant behavioral procedures.</p> <p>Results: Brain circuits involved in the induction of preferences for stimuli associated with electrical stimulation of the LPBe appear to functionally and neurochemically differ from those activated by electrical stimulation of the LH.</p> <p>Interpretation: We discuss the possible involvement of the LPBe in processing emotional-affective aspects of the brain reward system.</p> <p>Conflict of interest: None</p>

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Drs. D. J. Nutt and P. Blier (Editors)
Journal of Psychopharmacology

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12 April 20, 2019

13 Dear Professors Blier and Nutt:

14
15 We are pleased to submit a re-revised version of our paper entitled “**Differential**
16 **rewarding effects of electrical stimulation of the lateral hypothalamus and**
17 **parabrachial complex: a functional characterization and the relevance of opioid**
18 **systems and dopamine” (JOP-2018-3666-R1), as requested. Changes/additions are**
19 **highlighted in red and deletions in gray. We enclose on separate pages our responses to**
20 **the comments of your reviewers with an account of the corresponding modifications to**
21 **the text.**

22
23 We are very grateful to reviewers for their insights and recommendations, which
24 have led to marked improvements in the quality and clarity of our manuscript.

25
26 If there are any further questions regarding our submittal, please do not hesitate to
27 contact us at the address shown on the title page. We look forward to your comments
28 and decision on our paper.

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37 With thanks, sincerely yours,

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42 Dr María Jose Simon.
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RESPONSE TO REVIEWERS

We are again very grateful to our reviewers for their comments and insights. We include our point-by-point responses below.

REVIEWER 2

1. P7L17: “CPP” should probably be changed to “CTP”.

This has been changed accordingly (now on page 11, paragraph 2 – in section 5).

“For example, in a study involving CTP in combination with optogenetic stimulation of the CeA, two lever-presses were simultaneously available to the animals: one associated with obtaining sucrose + optogenetic stimulation of the CeA and the other with obtaining sucrose alone [...] (Robinson et al., 2014)”.

2. Same paragraph: I still find it strange to have a clearly operant procedure in a section titled “Reward induced by non-operant procedures”...

The title has been preserved, and the paragraph on operant procedures has been moved to another section (section 5, page 11, second paragraph).

3. P7L31-33: the choice procedure itself in Robinson et al’s study does not dissociate between hedonic and motivational properties of sucrose+stimulation. That was demonstrated with “facial liking response” that is not useful with drugs or ICSS.

We agree with the reviewer. Our interpretation of this paragraph is that, because the animals received sucrose in both cases, the difference in choice may be attributable to the enhancing motivational effect of optogenetic stimulation associated with one of the two options. The text has been changed as follows (section 5, page 11, second paragraph):

“A relationship of sucrose intake with opiate activity and motivational circuits has also been demonstrated at other brain sites. For example, in a study involving CTP in combination with optogenetic stimulation of the CeA, two lever-presses were simultaneously available to the animals: one associated with obtaining sucrose + optogenetic stimulation of the CeA and the other with obtaining sucrose alone. Although sucrose was available with both options, the animals preferred the former option, suggesting that optogenetic stimulation of this area may have enhanced the motivation to obtain sucrose (Robinson et al., 2014). It has also been reported that animals worked harder to earn sucrose + laser in a separate breakpoint procedure designed to test the intensity of motivation (Robinson et al., 2014)”.

4. P8L14-33: The location of the cited studies is better, but there is still no support for the fact that animals will self-administer drugs that are potentially addictive in humans.

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3 The aim of this paragraph was to introduce the involvement of
4 neurotransmitters other than dopamine in reward and to indicate the
5 connection of animal studies with the addiction problems suffered by humans.
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9 **5. P8L17: Parentheses need to be closed after "... etc."**

10 This typographic error has been corrected, as follows (page 8, section 4,
11 paragraph 3rd.)

12 *"Drugs of abuse that cause addiction in humans (e.g., cocaine, amphetamine, heroin,*
13 *nicotine, etc.)"*.
14
15

16
17 **6. P11L22-38: Is there really evidence that opioid receptor antagonists can**
18 **block the molecular adaptations induce by food restriction? They clearly prevent**
19 **the reduction in LHSS threshold, but I am not sure Carr's group reported that the**
20 **molecular changes are blocked as well.**
21

22 We have deleted the last sentence in this paragraph. Although the review by
23 Carr's group (2011) reported that food restriction and the compulsive use of sucrose,
24 with their concomitant neuroadaptations, can alter the function of mesoacumbens
25 dopamine neurons, it addressed the effects on GluR1 and AMPA receptors and made no
26 reference to the opiate system (which would also be affected by sucrose intake).(Page
27 12, first paragraph).
28
29

30
31 **7. P11L33: "Berman et al., 1995" should be 1994.**

32 This error has been corrected (page 11, last paragraph):

33 *"In fact, this effect can be blocked by the administration of both general (naltrexone)*
34 *and selective agonists (for mu and kappa receptors) (Berman et al., 1994;..."*
35
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38 **8. P21L26-42: Garcia et al.'s study – I am not sure about the interpretation**
39 **here. It is not clear which effects "disappeared" with the addition of time delay.**
40 **The 6 h "delay" in Garcia et al.'s study, was the interval between the "choice" and**
41 **"reversal" tests. The reversal test demonstrated the association of rewarding (and**
42 **aversive) effects of LPBe stimulation to place (rather than taste) stimuli. There**
43 **was no "learning" expectation in that second test, as in both tests there was no**
44 **stimulation of the LPBe. I therefore do not understand how the Garcia et al. study**
45 **is relevant to the flexibility of the acquired memory, and the impact of delays. In**
46 **other words, would you expect the results to be different if the reversal test would**
47 **have been presented first, with no delay (a serious omission in Garcia et al.'s**
48 **study)?**
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52 During the acquisition phase in the study by García and colleagues, the
53 animals were offered, in a contiguous manner, flavor A + electrical LPBe stimulation
54 and flavor B + absence of electrical stimulation on alternate days. After various pairing
55 trials, the animals underwent test I, in which the two flavors were offered
56 simultaneously with no associated electrical stimulation. In this test, the animals chose
57 the flavor/localization associated with the electrical stimulation. In test II, conducted
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3 after a 6-hour interval, the two flavors were again offered simultaneously but their
4 positions were inverted, allowing for three possible outcomes: 1) learning of flavor-
5 stimulation association (selection of flavor in inverse position); 2) learning of
6 association between burette position and stimulation (selection of liquid offered in same
7 position as before, regardless of the flavor); 3) Extinction of learning (random selection
8 of liquid). The results obtained indicate that the second outcome was achieved.
9

10
11 We do not know what would have happened if the reversal test had been
12 presented first: either the result would have been the same (choice based on the position
13 of the burettes) or the flavor would have behaved as a distractor stimulus, with the
14 animals needing a larger number of learning trials. In fact, in a mirror experiment in
15 which we explored the result of forcing animals to acquire flavor-related learning by
16 changing the position of the burettes (Simon et al., 2013), a larger number of learning
17 trials was needed, although the animals finally learned the task.
18

19
20 It should also be noted that temporal contiguity was needed during the
21 acquisition phase. In another experiment (unpublished results), the acquisition trials
22 consisted of the presentation of flavor A + delay of 15' + electrical stimulation and, on
23 alternate days, flavor B + delay of 15' + absence of electrical stimulation. In this
24 experiment, the animals did not learn the task.
25

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27 These features are compatible with a lack of flexibility on these learning
28 mechanisms, which are in concordance with the results obtained by Mediavilla et al.
29 (2001) using natural stimuli.
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3 REVIEWER 3:
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5 We are very grateful to the comments of our reviewer, which have helped us to
6 strengthen and clarify our paper.
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9 **Mayor comments:**

10 We now cite and discuss the study by Han et al (2018) on page 21, second and
11 third paragraph:
12

13
14 *“A recent study by Han et al. (2018) also addressed the study of neural circuits
15 involved in reward of visceral-vagal origin. By using optogenetic stimulation of the
16 vagus nerve in combination with cell-specific transneuronal tracing, these authors
17 induced preferences for stimuli associated with flavor and spatial tasks and achieved
18 satiation and self-stimulation behaviors. As a result, they identified a right-vagus-
19 parabrachial-nigrostriatal circuit mediated by the dorsal LPB that projected towards
20 nigrostriatal dopaminergic cells (Han et al., 2018). However, they found no connection
21 between the LPBe and the substantia nigra pars compacta (Han et al., 2018), an
22 outcome that agrees in some way with our findings reported throughout this section, in
23 which electrical stimulation of the LPBe appeared to activate a system other than the
24 substantia nigra and mediated by opiates instead of dopamine (Simon et al., 2007;
25 2008; 2009; 2011; 2013; García et al., 2014)”.*
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31 We also now refer to the drawbacks in interpreting the results of electrical
32 stimulation (page 16, last paragraph):
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35 *“...this led our group to use Electrical Stimulation to activate this region and analyze
36 its possible participation in rewarding brain mechanisms (Simon et al., 2007; 2008;
37 2011; 2013; García et al., 2014). However, electrical stimulation usually depolarizes
38 not only body cells but also fibers of passage in the vicinity of the electrode, which may
39 limit the precision of our results (Wise and Rompré, 1989; Yeomans, 1990)”.*
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44 **Specific comments**

45
46 **Page 3, line 40: Delete “first.” The original discovery of ICSS entailed stimulation
47 of a site in the septum.**
48

49 We have deleted the word “first”. This sentence now reads:

50
51 *“Anatomical regions supporting ICSS were located around the medial forebrain bundle
52 (MFB) (Gallistel et al., 1981; Wise and Rompré, 1989; Phillips and Fibiger, 1989)”.*
53

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55 **Page 4, line 3: The collision experiments that provided conduction-velocity
56 estimates for reward-related MFB fibers linking the LH and VTA were behavioral**
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3 **studies, not electrophysiological studies. It is the action potentials that collided, not**
4 **the pulses.**
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6 We have modified this sentence accordingly (page 4, first paragraph):
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8
9 *“...activation of the mesoaccumbal dopaminergic rewarding system has been confirmed*
10 *by classical lesion and/or stimulation experiments in combination with **behavioral and***
11 ***recording procedures (e.g., microdialysis or voltammetry)”**.*
12

13
14 **Page 5, line 3: What do the authors mean by “space-time signals?”**

15 We refer to signals from multiple rewarding stimuli present simultaneously or at
16 different times. We now use the term “*multidimensional signals*”.

17
18
19 *“which would integrate **multidimensional signals** and the subjective effort that*
20 *leads individuals to perform goal-directed behaviors (Hernandez et al, 2006;*
21 *2007;2012; Berridge and Kringelbach, 2015; Castro et al., 2015, among others)”*.
22

23
24 **Page 5, line 52. The experimenter has no way of knowing with certainty what the**
25 **mice were experiencing. The taste-reactivity measures concern observable**
26 **behaviors; what experiences they reflect is a controversial inference.**
27

28 We are grateful for this observation. This sentence now reads (page 5, last paragraph):
29

30
31 *“In addition, knock-out mice unable to synthesize the enzyme tyrosine hydroxylase ~~were~~*
32 *~~capable of experiencing~~ **showed facial expressions consistent with affective/hedonic***
33 *reactions...”*
34

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36 **Page 6, line 1: Delete “with.”**

37 We have modified this sentence as suggested (page 6, first paragraph):
38

39
40 *“severe hypoactive and hypophagic animals developed a strong contextual preference*
41 *for morphine when administered caffeine”*.
42

43
44 **Page 6, line 17. Replace “some authors” with “Wise.” (He is one individual, not a**
45 **group.)**

46
47 *“Indeed, **Wise** more recently affirmed that ‘pleasure may not be a necessary correlate of*
48 *dopamine elevations’ (Wise, 2008)”*.
49

50
51 **Page 6, lines 38-40. Which way does the arrow of causation point? Isn’t the**
52 **operant behavior learned because the stimulation induces a rewarding effect and**
53 **not the other way around?**
54

55 The text has been modified to clarify this point. It now reads (page 6, paragraph 3):
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3 *“...the electrical stimulation has a rewarding effect that can be manifested not only by*
4 *the learning of an operant behavior but also by other procedures in which it is*
5 *associated with a specific cue or context”.*
6
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8 **Page 14, lines 35-36. Change “soma” to “somata” (plural form).**

9
10 This has been done (page 15, first paragraph):

11
12 *“These are mainly bipolar neurons with **somata** in the nodose ganglion, ...”*

13
14 **Page 24, lines 8-15: This is an unnecessarily vague and rather odd way to describe**
15 **the opponent-process theory, which is sketched more clearly a few sentences later.**

16
17 We have deleted this sentence in the revised manuscript. This paragraph now reads:
18 (page X, paragraph Y)

19
20
21 *“According to this theory, mechanisms that support addictive behavior, characterized*
22 *by compulsive seeking behavior, loss of control, and a negative emotional state, would*
23 *be temporarily connected in an opponent loop containing...”*

24
25
26 **Page 26, lines 12-17. The authors are providing Salamone’s interpretation of his**
27 **data. However, Hernandez et al. (Hernandez, G., Breton, Y.-A., Conover, K., &**
28 **Shizgal, P. (2010). PLoS ONE, 5(11). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0015081>)**
29 **have shown that these data could just as readily have arisen from vertical rescaling**
30 **or lateral displacement of the underlying reward-growth function.**

31
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33 We now refer to the hypothesis of Hernandez et al. in this paragraph (page 26, last
34 paragraph):

35
36
37 *“Conversely, drugs that increase dopaminergic transmission tend to facilitate behaviors*
38 *requiring a high effort (Salamone et al., 2016; **Hernandez et al., 2010**) or low subjective*
39 *opportunity (**Hernandez et al., 2010**)”.*

40
41
42 **Page 26, lines 35-49: The key point made by the experiments applying the reward-**
43 **mountain model to data obtained following perturbation of dopaminergic**
44 **neurotransmission is that the change in reward seeking does not reflect a drug-**
45 **induced alteration in the sensitivity of brain reward circuitry but rather a rescaling**
46 **of reward intensity, a change in subjective effort cost, and/or a change in the value**
47 **of alternate activities. This is explained most clearly in Hernandez et al.**
48 **(Hernandez, G., Breton, Y.-A., Conover, K., & Shizgal, P. (2010). PLoS ONE,**
49 **5(11). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0015081>).**

50
51
52 We have rewritten this paragraph to take account of these points (page 27, last
53 paragraph):

54
55
56 *“In this regard, the reward-mountain model predicts that changes in dopamine release*
57 *can modify the pursuit of brain stimulation reward by rescaling the reward intensity,*
58
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3 *and this may involve a decrease in subjective effort and/or a reduction in the value of*
4 *alternate activities (Hernandez et al., 2010; 2012)]. These modifications in dopamine*
5 *tone do not appear to correlate well with variables related to affective aspects*
6 *(Scardochio et al., 2015).*
7
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10 **Page 27, line 31. No one can know what “hedonic feelings” are experienced by**
11 **decerebrate rats. Taste reactivity can be measured, but the subjective experience**
12 **this reflects remains hidden.**
13

14 As suggested, we have modified the sentence: (page X, paragraph Y)

15
16 “Given that facial expressions consistent with hedonic reactions **feelings** can be
17 generated in decerebrated animals at brainstem level (Grill and Norgren, 1978; Castro et
18 al., 2015)”.

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For Peer Review

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3 **TITLE: Differential rewarding effects of electrical stimulation of the lateral**
4 **hypothalamus and parabrachial complex: functional characterization and the**
5 **relevance of opioid systems and dopamine**
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30 †In memoriam.
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ABSTRACT:

Background: *Since the discovery of rewarding intracranial self-stimulation by Olds and Milner, extensive data have been published on the biological basis of reward. Although participation of the mesolimbic dopaminergic system is well documented, its precise role has not been fully elucidated, and some authors have proposed the involvement of other neural systems in processing specific aspects of reinforced behavior.*

Aims and methods: *We reviewed published data, including our own findings, on the rewarding effects induced by electrical stimulation of the lateral hypothalamus (LH) and of the external lateral parabrachial area (LPBe) -a brainstem region involved in processing the rewarding properties of natural and artificial substances-, and compared its functional characteristics as observed in operant and non-operant behavioral procedures.*

Results: *Brain circuits involved in the induction of preferences for stimuli associated with electrical stimulation of the LPBe appear to functionally and neurochemically differ from those activated by electrical stimulation of the LH.*

Interpretation: *We discuss the possible involvement of the LPBe in processing emotional-affective aspects of the brain reward system.*

Conflict of interest: None

Keywords: Motivation, Reward, lateral hypothalamus (LH), external lateral parabrachial nucleus (LPBe), opioids, dopamine.

1- Introduction

Organisms have evolved neurobiological mechanisms capable of detecting, processing, and evaluating the presence of natural stimuli essential for individual and/or species survival, generating rewarding reactions in their presence and triggering responses for their acquisition (Shizgal et al., 2001; Berthoud and Münzberg, 2011).

Affective reactions to reinforcing stimuli can give rise to the acquisition of new learning, which tends to identify cues of its availability and thereby increase the possibility of access to them (Bindra, 1974; Dayan & Balleine, 2002; Berridge, 2018). These motivational processes appear to be driven by complex mechanisms that can include various components with specific neural branches of a network involving common elements and likely interactions among them (White and Milner, 1992; Waraczynski, 2006; Berthoud and Munzberg, 2011; Salamone et al., 2016).

2- The brain reward system and dopamine

In 1954, James Olds and Peter Milner made the landmark discovery of rewarding brain stimulation (or intracranial self-stimulation, ICSS), which has proven to be a powerful tool for understanding the neurobiological bases of reward (Olds and Milner, 1954; De Haan, 2010). Anatomical regions supporting ICSS were **first** located around the medial forebrain bundle (MFB) (Gallistel et al., 1981; Wise and Rompré, 1989; Phillips and Fibiger, 1989), and it was subsequently found that this operant behavior can be elicited by electrodes located in many other areas, from the olfactory bulb to the nucleus of the solitary tract (NST) and cerebellum (Gallistel et al., 1981; Wise and Rompré, 1989; Phillips and Fibiger, 1989; Ikemoto, 2010; Vlachou and Markou, 2011 -for a review) (**Figure 1**).

Although ICSS can stimulate neurons containing different neurotransmitters (Stein & Wise, 1969; Yeomans et al., 1993; Ikemoto, 2010; Vlachou and Markou,

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3 2011), trans-synaptic (indirect) activation of the mesoaccumbal dopaminergic rewarding
4 system has been confirmed by classical lesion and/or stimulation experiments in
5
6 combination with behavioral and recording procedures (e.g., microdialysis or
7
8 voltammetry) (Wise and Rompré, 1989; Shizgal, 1989; Yeomans et al., 1993; Gallistel
9
10 et al., 1996; Ikemoto, 2010; Berridge and Kringelbach, 2015).
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15 Brain areas activated by self-stimulation of the LH have been examined using
16
17 immunohistochemistry [C-Fos] (Flores et al., 1997; Arvanitogiannis et al., 1997; 2000;
18
19 Hunt and McGregor, 1998), glycogen phosphorylase histochemistry (Konkle et al.,
20
21 1999), 2DG autoradiography (Gallistel et al., 1985), and functional neuroimaging
22
23 (Kolodziej et al., 2014) confirming an indirect activation of the mesoaccumbal
24
25 dopamine. In addition, a quantitative autoradiographic study observed that ICSS of the
26
27 lateral hypothalamus (LH) induces plastic changes in dopaminergic neurons of different
28
29 brain areas, especially in D1 dopaminergic receptors (Simon et al., 2016) [See **Table 1**
30
31 and **Figure 2**].
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35 Reward is currently considered as a complex functional process with many
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37 dissociable components [e.g., hedonic impact, learning, incentive motivation, seeking,
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39 or goal-directed related behaviors...] that may simultaneously or successively intervene
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41 in the behavioral reward cycle (Waraczynski, 2006; Berridge and Kringelbach, 2015;
42
43 Castro et al., 2015). The specific role of dopamine in relation to this process remains a
44
45 controversial issue and warrants further research (Waraczynski, 2006; Hernandez et al.,
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47 2007; Ikemoto, 2010; Smith et al., 2011; Salamone and Correa, 2012; Berridge and
48
49 Kringelbach, 2015; Morales and Margolis, 2017).
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54 It has been suggested that the dopaminergic mesolimbic system may not be
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56 related to the specific encoding of the rewarding or hedonic value *per se* but rather to
57
58 other aspects, such as: a) the novelty signal associated with the anticipation of reward
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3 (Schultz et al., 1997), b) behavioral arousal and/or seeking mechanisms (Berridge and
4 Robinson, 1998; Salamone, 1994; Salamone et al., 2016); and/or c) the incentive
5 component, which would integrate **multidimensional signals** and the subjective effort
6 that leads individuals to perform goal-directed behaviors (Hernandez et al., 2006;
7 2007;2012; Berridge and Kringelbach, 2015; Castro et al., 2015, among others).

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15 In accordance with this hypothesis, some studies showed that electrical
16 stimulation of the LH elicited food intake but did not enhance pleasure reactions
17 (Berridge and Valenstein, 1991). Moreover, genetically engineered mice lacking
18 dopamine had difficulties in carrying out goal-directed behaviors, although seeking
19 behaviors were restored after the local administration of dopamine (Robinson et al.,
20 2005; 2006). In addition, mice with a genetic disruption of dopamine transporter [DAT]
21 and a consequent increase in synaptic DA not only required fewer trials to learn an
22 incentive runway task but also ran faster to the goal and were better at avoiding
23 distractions (Peciña et al., 2003).

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It has also been reported that pharmacological dopamine blockade or even
complete destruction of the DA mesolimbic system did not diminish facial expressions
of hedonic impact (positive affective reactions), measured in a "taste reactivity test", a
procedure that allows the recording of orofacial reactions to innately and learned
gustative stimuli in human infants and animals (Grill and Norgren, 1978; Peciña et al.,
1997; Berridge and Robinson, 1998)..

In addition, knock-out mice unable to synthesize the enzyme tyrosine
hydroxylase ~~were capable of experiencing~~ *showed facial expressions consistent with*
affective/hedonic reactions to taste stimuli such as sucrose and/or saccharine, even in
the absence of dopamine (Cannon and Palmiter, 2003). In a related study, dopamine-
deficient and therefore severely hypoactive and hypophagic animals developed a strong

1
2
3 contextual preference for morphine when administered ~~with~~ caffeine or a dopaminergic
4 precursor during the testing phase (Hnasko et al. 2005; Cannon and Bseikri, 2004).
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8 Taken together, the above findings suggest that dopaminergic activity may not
9
10 be essential for processing positive hedonic reactions in animals showing self
11 stimulation of the LH or other sites (Peciña et al., 1997; Maldonado et al., 1997;
12 Cannon and Palmiter, 2003; Hnasko et al., 2005), as initially assumed (Wise, 1982;
13 Cannon and Palmiter, 2003; Hnasko et al., 2005), as initially assumed (Wise, 1982;
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‘*pleasure may not be a necessary correlate of dopamine elevations*’ (Wise, 2008).

3- Reward induced by non-operant procedures

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24 In their initial observations, Olds and Milner reported that animals not only
25 showed no sign of rejection but also repeatedly returned to the corner where they had
26 received the electrical stimulation (Olds and Milner, 1954; De Haan, 2010). This result
27 was replicated in other experiments in which groups of rats were placed in a T-shaped
28 maze and stimulated upon entry into a previously selected arm of the maze, for which
29 they developed a clear preference (Olds, 1956).
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37 Accordingly, ~~the rewarding effect of electrical stimulation can be induced not~~
38 ~~only by the learning of an operant behavior but also by administration of electrical~~
39 ~~stimulation in association with a particular location or context (Olds, 1956)~~ **the**
40 **electrical stimulation has a rewarding effect that can be manifested not only by the**
41 **learning of an operant behavior but also by other procedures in which it is associated**
42 **with a specific cue or context** (Olds, 1956). This second procedure, later known as
43 Conditioned Place Preference (CPP), can be induced through association of the
44 rewarding properties of a stimulus, treatment, drug, or substance with specific
45 environmental cues, which are initially neutral (Bardo and Bevins, 2000; Tzschentke,
46 2007). In another non-operant procedure, called Conditioned Taste Preference [CTP],
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3 the stimulation can be associated with one of two gustatory stimuli (Cubero and Puerto,
4 2000; Simon et al., 2007; 2008). In all of these rate-free learning procedures, a
5 recording is made of the time spent by the animal in the stimulated compartment or the
6 amount of liquid consumed after the associative learning, and this measure appears to be
7 more closely related to 'consummatory' or 'pleasant' reactions than to 'preparatory' or
8 'seeking' behaviors (Tzschentke, 2007; Dayan and Berridge, 2014).
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12 ~~Some authors have employed CTP procedures to assess the rewarding~~
13 ~~nature of ICSS of the LH, which was associated with one of two flavors (Ettenberg,~~
14 ~~1980). In another study involving CTP in combination with optogenetic stimulation of~~
15 ~~the CeA, two lever-presses were simultaneously available to the animals: one associated~~
16 ~~with obtaining sucrose + optogenetic stimulation of the CeA and the other with~~
17 ~~obtaining sucrose alone (Robinson et al., 2014). Although animals preferred the former~~
18 ~~option, they failed to establish any self-stimulation behavior not associated with an~~
19 ~~external source of reward, suggesting that the stimulation may have enhanced the~~
20 ~~motivation to obtain sucrose and implying its involvement in processing a component~~
21 ~~other than the hedonic (Robinson et al., 2014).~~
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40 ~~Taken together,~~ **These experiments demonstrated that CPP and CTP procedures**
41 **can be useful to discriminate specific components of rewarding electrical stimulation in**
42 **different areas of the brain** (Tzschentke, 2007; Dayan and Berridge, 2014). **In fact, they**
43 **procedures** **have been widely used to study preferences for** drugs of abuse in animals
44 (Jaeger and Van der Kooy, 1993; Nader et al., 1996; McBride et al., 1999; Tzschentke,
45 2007), for natural stimuli such as food and drinks (Spiteri et al., 2000), for social and
46 sexual interactions (Garcia-Horsman et al., 2008), and for electrical stimulation
47 (Ettenberg, 1980; Cubero and Puerto, 2000; Simon et al., 2007; 2008; 2009; 2011;
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3 2013; Garcia et al., 2013) and may contribute to further research on this issue (Dayan
4 and Berridge, 2014).
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7 **4-Opiates and brain stimulation reward**

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10 In parallel to the above-cited studies centered on the dopaminergic mesolimbic
11 system, researchers began to focus on other neurotransmitter systems that could
12 participate in processing these affective aspects of reward (Peciña and Smith, 2010;
13 Berthoud and Münzberg, 2011; Castro et al., 2015; Berridge and Kringelbach, 2015;
14 Fields and Margolis, 2015; Morales and Margolis, 2017; Darcq and Kiefer, 2018).
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21 Drugs of abuse that cause addiction in humans (e.g., cocaine, amphetamine,
22 heroin, nicotine, etc.) can be self-administered by laboratory animals in operant
23 procedures and modulate ICSS behavior by changing rate/frequency curves and brain
24 stimulation thresholds (Carlezon and Chartoff, 2007; Vlachou and Markou, 2011;
25 Negus and Miller, 2014). Opiates are among these highly addictive substances and have
26 potentially serious health consequences (Bodnar, 2017 -for a review-). Their action on
27 opioid receptors can induce reinforcing effects by increasing the likelihood of
28 behavioral responses associated with them (Negus and Miller, 2014; Fields and
29 Margolis, 2015; Darcq and Kiefer, 2018).
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42 With respect to the specific relationship between these opioid substances and
43 ICSS, initial studies only observed changes in the lever-press rate when high doses of
44 opioid substances were administered (Schaefer, 1988). Cazala et al. investigated the
45 effect of different doses of the opiate antagonist naloxone (0.5, 2, and 10 mg/Kg) on
46 operant approach-escape behaviors in a shuttle box after LH or periaqueductal gray
47 (PAG) stimulation (Cazala and Davis, 1991). They found that intermediate doses
48 blocked escape responses alone, whereas very high doses blocked both approach and
49 escape behaviors (Cazala and Davis, 1991). Likewise, the administration of 10 and 20
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3 mg/kg naloxone caused a dose-dependent shift in the rate-frequency curve of VTA self-
4 stimulation but did not completely block the operant behavior (Bielajew et al., 2003).
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6 Similar results were obtained in a study using specific kappa receptor ligands
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8 (Todtenkopf et al., 2004).
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12 In another study, Easterling and Holtzman demonstrated that acute morphine
13 administration produced a small decrease in the titration point for ICSS behavior (the
14 lowest stimulation frequency needed to maintain this operant behavior), reporting that
15 this effect progressively diminished over time (Easterling and Holtzman, 1997). In
16 addition, they found that cumulative doses of naltrexone (opioid antagonist) during the
17 course of ICSS only generate minimal dose-independent increases in the titration point,
18 observing that this effect also decreased with longer time (Easterling and Holtzman,
19 1997; 2004). These results suggest a weak and non-determinant role of opiates in ICSS
20 of the LH, that disappear over time and that opiate antagonists do not completely block
21 this-behavior, even at high doses (Schaefer, 1988; Cazala & Davis, 1991; Easterling and
22 Holtzman, 1997; 2004; Bielajew et al., 2003; Wiebelhaus et al., 2016).
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37 In addition, recent studies combining LH ICSS with quantitative autoradiography
38 of specific D1, D2, or mu receptors have again raised questions about the relevance of
39 the opioid systems in electrical self-stimulation of the LH (Simon et al., 2016). After
40 ICSS of the LH, administration of the opiate agonist ³H-DAMGO showed no significant
41 differences in the concentration of mu receptors between self-stimulated and control
42 animals across a wide range of brain sections from the whole rostrocaudal axis;
43 however, significant differences were observed after administration of the specific D1-
44 receptor antagonist ³H-SCH-23390 in the NAC shell, caudate-putamen, ventral
45 pallidum, and medial globus pallidus (Simon et al., 2016) (See **Figure 3**). These data
46 are compatible with observations of few modifications in the activity of mu receptors in
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3 two groups of animals from related breeds that differed in operant response rates (ICSS
4 of LH) (Gross-Isserof et al., 1992). Thus, differences were only significant in the NAC
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6 (Gross-Isserof et al., 1992).
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10 Furthermore, we employed a CPP procedure to assess the importance of the
11 opioid system in rewarding electrical stimulation of the LH (administered by the
12 experimenter) and showed that animals preferred the compartment associated with
13 electrical stimulation of the LH (Simón et al., 2011). However, this effect was not
14 blocked by naloxone, even at elevated doses of 10 mg/kg (Simón et al., 2011) (**Figure**
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23 **4**).

24 Taken together, these data on the involvement of opioids in self-stimulation of
25 the LH might be compatible with a dual action on dopamine-dependent and dopamine-
26 independent mechanisms of reward (Wassum et al., 2009; Fields and Margolis, 2015;
27 Ide et al., 2017) that cannot be completely blocked by the effect of antagonists in this
28 region.
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35 **5-Involvement of opioids in natural rewarding mechanisms**

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37 The hypothalamus is considered to be a critical region for homeostatic behaviors
38 and rewards (Shizgal et al., 2001; Castro et al., 2015; Stuber and Wise, 2016). Initial
39 studies in this research area showed that electrolytic or chemical lesions of the LH
40 suppressed food and water intake, whereas its electrical stimulation could induce
41 feeding and/or drinking behaviors in satiated animals (Hoebel and Teitelbaum, 1962;
42 Stuber and Wise, 2016 -for a review-).
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51 The involvement of opioids in the regulation of natural rewards, such as food
52 intake, has been well documented for more than 30 years (Gosnell and Levine, 2009;
53 Peciña and Smith, 2010 -for a review-). Various studies have attributed opiates present
54 in the LH with an intake-activating role, generating the overconsumption of palatable
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3 foods that might become 'potentially addictive' and contributing to maintain the
4 consumption once initiated (Papadouka and Carr, 1994; Carr and Papadouka, 1994;
5 Gosnell and Levine, 2009; Ikeda et al., 2015). These effects appear to be related to their
6 action on dopamine-dependent circuits involved in deficit and/or motivational seeking
7 processes (Gosnell and Levine, 2009; Ikeda et al., 2015). In fact, sucrose consumption
8 produces plastic changes, including the upregulation of mu and D1 dopamine receptors
9 (Colantuoni et al., 2001; Olson et al., 2007), and the release of dopamine during
10 instrumental (operant) behaviors for food (Salamone et al., 1994; Sokolowski et al.,
11 1998).

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24 A relationship of sucrose intake with opiate activity and motivational circuits has
25 also been demonstrated at other brain sites. For example, in a study involving CTP in
26 combination with optogenetic stimulation of the CeA, two lever-presses were
27 simultaneously available to the animals: one associated with obtaining sucrose +
28 optogenetic stimulation of the CeA and the other with obtaining sucrose alone.
29 Although sucrose was available with both options, the animals preferred the former
30 option, suggesting that optogenetic stimulation of this area may have enhanced the
31 motivation to obtain sucrose (Robinson et al., 2014). It has also been reported that
32 animals worked harder to earn sucrose + laser in a separate breakpoint procedure
33 designed to test the intensity of motivation (Robinson et al., 2014).

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47 In this line, the manipulation of motivational mechanisms, such as chronic food
48 restriction, has been found to activate opioid receptors in an opioid dopaminergic-
49 dependent system, which in turn produces changes in dopaminergic D1 and glutamergic
50 receptors of the NAC (Haberny & Carr, 2005; Ouyang et al., 2017). In fact, this effect
51 can be blocked by the administration of both general (naltrexone) and selective agonists
52 (for mu and kappa receptors) (Berman et al., 1994; Carr and Papadouka, 1994; Carr,
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3 2002). ~~and may correspond to the generation of adverse neuroadaptations and~~
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5 ~~locomotor-activating effects in striatal dopaminergic neurons (Carr, 2011).~~
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8 In summary, various studies have demonstrated that not only the electrical
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10 stimulation of certain brain regions (such as the LH) but also natural reinforcers (food)
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12 and drugs of abuse can share the capacity to induce increases in DA release in the NAC
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14 (Salamone, 1994; Sokolowski et al., 1998; Cameron et al., 2014). Their differential
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16 release pattern may be more or less transient according to the activation of microcircuits
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18 of dopaminergic neurons that appear to be related to this motivational or seeking
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20 component of reward (Spanagel et al., 1992; Olson et al., 2007; Cameron et al., 2014;
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22 Fields and Margolis, 2015).
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26 In this regard, Carelli et al. described a functional dissociation in the NAC
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28 between neural microsystems involved in processing natural rewards (food and water)
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30 and those involved in processing artificial rewards (cocaine) (Carelli et al., 2000;
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32 Carelli, 2002; Cameron et al., 2014). Using the same operant response (lever pressing)
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34 to obtain food or self-administer cocaine, they recorded the trigger patterns of NAC
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36 cells and observed that they were determined by the nature of the reward and by its
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38 associated environmental cues (Carelli, 2002; Cameron et al., 2014). Moreover,
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40 although natural reinforcers and drugs of abuse appear to share the capacity to generate
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42 dopamine release in the NAC shell, the response induced by the former progressively
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44 decreases, while the DA response induced by drugs remains robust after every
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46 administration (Pontieri et al., 1995). These results led to the consideration of addiction
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48 as a special case of "overlearning" (Hyman et al., 2006).
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54 This dissociation has also been behaviorally verified in analyses of the effects of
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56 food or morphine preference in a CPP paradigm, in which experimental animals showed
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58 a preference for the compartment associated with the drug and also for the natural
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3 reinforcer (Spiteri et al., 2000). However, while animals remained in close contact with
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5 the environmental setting in which they had experienced physiological reactions
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7 associated with morphine administration, their behavior was different in relation to
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9 natural rewards, with frequent entry into the reward-associated compartment of the
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11 maze and numerous exploratory (rearing, sniffing) and approach behaviors (Spiteri, et
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13 al., 2000).
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17 In conclusion, studies on the role of opioids in **natural and/or** homeostatic LH-
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19 related mechanisms indicate their possible relationship with activation of a dopamine-
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21 related system, possibly connected to goal-directed behaviors. However, as already
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23 noted, some authors have also observed the presence of opiate hedonic hotspots (NAC
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25 shell, ventral pallidum) embedded in this mesolimbic system, which may generate
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27 and/or increase affective reactions to rewarding taste or smell stimuli from food
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29 (Wassum et al., 2009; Peciña and Smith, 2010; Smith et al., 2011).
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32 33 **6- Involvement of the Vagal-Parabrachial system in rewarding processes**

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35 Nutritional behavior allows organisms to recover the continuous energy
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37 expenditure produced by the metabolism of body cells and requires systems specialized
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39 in the detection and analysis of substances reaching the digestive system (Shizgal et al.,
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41 2001; Castro et al., 2015).
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45 Information from the gastrointestinal tract can be transmitted to the brain *via* two
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47 complementary substrates: a rapid neural system and a slower humoral pathway, which
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49 make some of their first synaptic contacts in brainstem regions of the NST and Area
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51 Postrema (AP), respectively (Fulwiler and Saper, 1984; De Lacalle & Saper, 2000). The
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53 information then passes to the next relay, the parabrachial complex, which receives
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55 relevant gustatory and visceral information for different motivational and/ or rewarding
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3 aspects of intake behavior (Fulwiler and Saper, 1984; Halsell and Travers, 1997; De
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5 Lacalle and Saper, 2000; Baird et al., 2001; Karimnamazi et al., 2002) (**Figure 5**).

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8 The differential involvement of these two systems in nutritional processes
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10 appears related to the type of substance and the experimental situation (Mediavilla et al.,
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12 2005). In this regard, "taste preference tests", which require the association of non-
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14 nutritive and innocuous taste stimuli (generally flavored water) with the intragastric or
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16 intra-intestinal administration of a visceral stimulus, allow the aversive or rewarding
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18 nature of viscerally administered substances to be analyzed (Mediavilla et al., 2005).

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21 Taste learning can be induced by using *sequential* or *concurrent* procedures. In
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23 *sequential* learning, the taste stimulus is associated with intragastric administrations on
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25 alternating days/sessions (Mediavilla et al. 2000; 2005; Zafra et al., 2002; 2007b). In the
26
27 *concurrent* modality, these stimuli are presented at the same time, pairing the intake of
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29 tastes with the simultaneous intragastric administration of either the visceral stimulus or
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31 an innocuous substance, e.g., physiological saline (Puerto et al., 1976; Mediavilla et al.,
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33 2000; Zafra et al., 2007a). Concurrent learning permits a rapid detection of biologically
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35 relevant substances in the upper gastrointestinal tract, allowing individuals to efficiently
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37 select food without waiting for the long-term benefits that result from its absorption
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39 (Puerto et al., 1976). Consequently, the neural pathway formed by vagal and spinal
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41 afferent fibers is essential when the task imposes important time demands and requires
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43 the rapid detection of the stimuli present in the upper gastrointestinal tract, although
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45 spinal fibers appear to be less important (Furness et al., 1999; Raybould, 2010; Zafra et
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47 al., 2016).

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50 The vagal system comprises nerve fibers connected to mechano-, chemo-, and
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52 osmo-receptors that can receive and calibrate the sensory components (pH or
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54 osmolality) of food as well as its micro- and macro-chemical nature (Furness et al.,
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3 1999; Raybould, 2010). These are mainly bipolar neurons with **somata** in the nodose
4 ganglion, a peripheral branch, and a central branch that terminates in the NST (Andrews
5 and Sanger, 2002). Glutamate, GABA, noradrenalin, and serotonin, among other
6 neurotransmitters, have been identified in NST endings alongside opiate receptors (μ
7 and, to a lesser extent, delta and kappa receptors (Mansour et al., 1995; Ozaki et al.,
8 2000; Andrews and Sanger, 2002; Bogdanova et al., 2015) and receptors for
9 cholecystikinin (CCK), glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1), glutamate, substance P,
10 prostaglandins, histamine, Y and YY neuropeptides, cannabinoids (CB1 and CB2), and
11 leptin, among others (Andrews and Sanger, 2002; Fromentin et al., 2012).

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24 With respect to opiate receptors, their density has been found to decrease after
25 vagal deafferentation or ganglionectomy (Dashwood et al., 1988), suggesting a
26 presynaptic localization on vagal afferents, although they have also been identified at
27 postsynaptic level. In fact, the presence of opiate peptides (enkephalins, β -endorphin)
28 has been demonstrated in second-order neurons in the intermediate-caudal region of the
29 NST (Velley et al., 1991; Ozaki et al., 2000). The utilization of complex retrograde
30 labeling techniques revealed that some of these enkephalinergic neurons project to the
31 parabrachial complex (Maley and Panneton, 1988).

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42 At the most lateral end of this pontine region, surrounding the upper cerebellar
43 peduncle, is the **external lateral parabrachial subnucleus [LPBe] (Figure 6)**
44 (Fulwiller and Saper, 1984; Bernard et al., 1996; De Lacalle and Saper, 2000;
45 Karimnamazi et al., 2002), whose activity can be modulated by gastric distension and/or
46 vagus nerve stimulation (Suemori et al., 1994; Saleh and Cechetto, 1996). Conversely,
47 LPBe activity is significantly attenuated by vagus nerve lesions (Yamamoto and Sawa,
48 2000a).

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3 The LPBe is known to be involved in processing a wide range of stimuli, most
4 of which may have affective value. It participates in analysis of the sensory and hedonic
5 characteristics of taste stimuli (Yamamoto et al., 1994; Halsell and Travers, 1997;
6 Sowards, 2004) and of different nutrients, such as intraduodenally administered glucose
7 (Wang et al., 1999), and intragastrically administered lactose and sucrose (Yamamoto
8 and Sawa 2000a; 2000b). Some hormones involved in regulating intake and nutritional
9 metabolism, such as CCK, galanin, Y and YY neuropeptides, and leptin also appear to
10 act *via* the LPBe (Li and Rowland, 1995; Trifunovich and Reilly, 2001; Elias et al.,
11 2000; Alhadeff et al., 2015), as do antimetabolic products such as mercaptoacetate
12 (Calingasan and Ritter, 1993). Finally, it has been observed that various brain areas,
13 including the LPBe, can be activated by the administration of drugs with a potential
14 intake-modulating role, including benzodiazepines (Söderpalm and Berridge, 2000),
15 fenfluramine (Li and Rowland, 1995; Simansky and Niclous, 2002), cannabinoids
16 (DiPatricio and Simansky, 2008), and opiates (Chamberlin et al., 1999; Chaijale et al.,
17 2013).

37 **7- Functional characterization of the LPBe**

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39 The aforementioned reports on the involvement of the LPBe in processing a
40 wide range of hedonic stimuli led our group to use Electrical Stimulation to activate this
41 region and analyze its possible participation in rewarding brain mechanisms (Simon et
42 al., 2007; 2008; 2011; 2013; García et al., 2014). **However, electrical stimulation
43 usually depolarizes not only body cells but also fibers of passage in the vicinity of the
44 electrode, which may limit the precision of our results (Wise and Rompré, 1989;
45 Yeomans, 1990)**".

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47 **Results of** These and other related experiments revealed that most of animals
48 showed a preference for **taste** stimuli associated with this stimulation in concurrent
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3 tasks (Simon et al., 2007; 2008; 2013; García et al., 2014). These data agree with the
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5 findings obtained by Grill and Norgren (1978) using taste reactivity tests, in which
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7 decerebrated animals displayed appetitive reactions at brainstem level when food was
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9 directly introduced into the oral cavity but did not exhibit seeking behaviors (Grill and
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11 Norgren, 1978). Data obtained by this procedure led various authors to consider these
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13 reactions as reflecting the hedonic impact of taste rather than merely sensory reflexes
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15 (Grill and Norgren, 1978; Castro et al., 2015).
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19 Our results are also compatible with observations that lesions of the lateral end
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21 of the parabrachial nucleus, including the LPBe, attenuated the overconsumption of
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23 highly palatable food induced by previous AP lesions (Edwards and Ritter, 1989) and
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25 blocked taste preferences induced by the administration of rewarding meals (Zafra et al.,
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27 2002). Furthermore, recording techniques at cell level identified neurons in the LPBe
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29 that can specifically process the sensory and/or hedonic properties of taste stimuli
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31 (Yamamoto et al., 1994; Halsell and Travers, 1997; Karimnamazi et al., 2002; Sowards,
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33 2004). In this sense, the rewarding effect of LPBe electrical stimulation (Simón et al.,
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35 2007; 2008; 2013) might be related to the modulation of taste-perception mechanisms in
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37 this area through changes in palatability (Parker et al., 1992).
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42 Alternatively, the rewarding effect of LPBe electrical stimulation may act as a
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44 substitute of visceral stimuli and/or its affective consequences (Simon et al., 2007; 2008)
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46 through the reception of visceral information from the NST (Fulwiller and Saper, 1984;
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48 De Lacalle and Saper, 2000). Indeed, an intact LPBe appears to be essential for rapid
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50 adjustments in neural systems related to short-term intake (Zafra et al., 2016) and for
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52 processing intragastrically administered rewarding nutrients (Zafra et al., 2002). As
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54 suggested by some authors, the LPBe may be part of a downstream circuit in which
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3 information on energy balance may interact with ascending visceral signals, promoting
4 a positive affective status in calorie-depleted animals (Garfield et al., 2015).
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8 Opiates have been found to play an important role in intake through their
9 differential action on mu/kappa receptors in the LPBe (Carr et al., 1991; Moufid-
10 Bellancourt et al., 1996) which undergo neuroadaptation under special conditions of
11 chronic food deprivation (Carr & Papadouka, 1994; Wolinsky et al., 1996). These data
12 may be compatible with our aforementioned findings of preferences for taste stimuli
13 associated with electrical stimulation (Simon et al., 2007; 2008), an effect that was
14 completely blocked by naloxone administration (Simón et al., 2007; 2011).
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24 Intake-modulating effects have also been reported for the intra-parabrachial
25 administration of benzodiazepines (midazolam) (Söderpalm and Berridge, 2000),
26 cannabinoids (DiPatricio and Simansky, 2008), and fenfluramine (Simansky and
27 Nicklous, 2002). Among other effects, these drugs may modify the assessment of
28 certain 'innately preferred' substances, acting on palatability (Soderpalm and Berridge,
29 2000; Wilson et al., 2003; DiPatricio and Simansky 2008). They may also increase the
30 hedonic properties of nutrients or diminish the state of 'discomfort' generated by
31 homeostatic imbalance (Carr et., 1991, Carr, 2002).
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42 The rewarding effect of LPBe electrical stimulation is observed not only in taste
43 tasks but also in a **concurrent conditioned place preference (cCPP)**, a variant of CPP
44 in which the animal can move freely throughout the maze but only receives stimulation
45 when it enters a previously selected compartment containing environmental (visual)
46 cues (Simon et al., 2007; 2009; 2011; García et al., 2014; Agüera et al., 2016). These
47 results suggest that preferences might not be specific to a single sensory modality
48 (Simon et al., 2007; 2009; 2011; 2013; García et al., 2014; Agüera et al., 2016). In fact,
49 some of these experiments showed that animals manifesting preferences for a taste
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3 stimulus associated with electrical LPBe stimulation after two CTP association trials
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5 consistently maintained this preference in a second phase in which they underwent a
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7 cCPP task (Simon et al., 2007) or a second CTP procedure with different taste stimuli
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9 (Simon et al., 2008).
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12 In the case of the experiments involving CTP procedures, there was no change in
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14 the left/right positioning of burettes with/without the stimulus associated with
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16 stimulation (Simon et al., 2007; 2008). We therefore explored whether the preferences
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18 established were related to taste stimuli or proprioceptive stimuli (right or left position
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20 of burettes). For this purpose, a new group of animals were trained in a similar CTP
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22 procedure and then underwent a second test in which the left/right position of the
23
24 burettes was inverted. According to the results obtained, the learning of animals was
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26 related to the place and not the taste stimuli. (García et al. 2014). On the other hand,
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28 another experiment in which the position of each burette varied among trials found that
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30 the animals acquired the learning but needed a larger number of trials (Simon et al.,
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32 2013). Overall, these findings suggest that animals are capable of developing a
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34 preference for either type of stimulus when associated with electrical stimulation of the
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36 LPBe but appear to have a biological predilection towards spatial cues (Simon et al.,
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38 2013; García et al., 2014).
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45 These data are compatible with other studies in which animals showed
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47 preference for the place associated with the intragastric infusion of liquids or foods or
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49 even with the presence of a sexual partner when the stimuli were administered
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51 immediately before confining the animals within a specific T-maze compartment
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53 (Arnold and Agmo, 1999; Spiteri et al., 2000; Garcia-Horsman et al., 2008). They are
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55 also in agreement with experiments that used this place procedure to explore the
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57 rewarding effects of substances of abuse (McBride et al., 1999; Tzschentke, 2007).
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3 Although LPBe electrical stimulation appears to generate preferences for
4 associated taste or place stimuli in most animals (Simon et al., 2007; 2008; 2009; 2011;
5 2013; García et al., 2014), we observed a small number of animals that consistently
6 preferred the taste or place that was not associated with stimulation (Simon et al., 2007;
7 2008; 2009). In other words, the electrical stimulation may have had an **aversive effect**
8 in some animals. In this regard, the LPBe contains relay fibers of the spino-(trigemino)
9 ponto-amygdaloid bundle, known to be specifically involved in processing the
10 affective-emotional, autonomic, and visceral components of pain (Bernard et al., 1991;
11 1996; Gauriau and Bernard, 2002; Li et al., 2006). It is therefore possible that a negative
12 affective status was generated in some animals through the activation of nociceptive
13 neurons in this system, explaining their avoidance behavior (Simon et al., 2007; 2008;
14 2009; 2011).

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31 The LPBe has been described as playing a key role in concurrent taste aversion
32 learning induced by aversive visceral stimuli administration (Mediavilla et al., 2000)
33 and as participating in a descending visceral system involved in appetite suppression
34 and the processing of 'unpleasant feelings' in unfavorable conditions for eating (Carter
35 et al., 2013). Moreover, the activation of kappa opiate receptors, also present in this
36 LPBe region, appears to have aversive effects, contrasting with the effects of mu
37 receptor activation (Moufid-Bellancourt et al., 1996; Darcq and Kieffer, 2018).

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47 It is possible that small changes in the placement of electrodes or in the current
48 used for electrical stimulation may differentially activate positive or negative cells that
49 react distinctly to the affective/hedonic properties of taste stimuli (Yamamoto et al.,
50 1994). It also feasible that the stimulation affects rewarding and/or aversive
51 motivational systems that are anatomically very close (Moufid-Bellancourt et al., 1996;
52 Wolinsky et al., 1996), as may be the case for the aforementioned visceral pathways
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3 generating signals of positive satiety (Garfield et al., 2015) and negative discomfort
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5 (Carter et al., 2013).
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8 A recent study by Han et al. (2018) also addressed the study of neural circuits
9
10 involved in reward of visceral-vagal origin. By using optogenetic stimulation of the
11
12 vagus nerve in combination with cell-specific transneuronal tracing, these authors
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14 induced preferences for stimuli associated with flavor and spatial tasks and achieved
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16 satiation and self-stimulation behaviors. As a result, they identified a right-vagus-
17
18 parabrachial-nigrostriatal circuit mediated by the dorsal LPB that projected towards
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20 nigrostriatal dopaminergic cells (Han et al., 2018). However, they found no connection
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22 between the LPBe and the substantia nigra pars compacta (Han et al., 2018), an
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24 outcome that agrees in some way with our findings reported throughout this section, in
25
26 which electrical stimulation of the LPBe appeared to activate a system other than the
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28 substantia nigra and mediated by opiates (Simon et al., 2007; 2008; 2009; 2011; 2013;
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30 García et al., 2014).
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35 We also carried out experiments aimed at training animals to self-administer
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37 current pulses to the LPBe while avoiding activation of an aversive system. Although
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39 the majority of animals did not display aversive behavior, it was not possible to induce
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41 ICSS, contrasting with the ready induction of this behavior using the LH (Simon et al.,
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43 2011) and with the results obtained by Han et al. (Han et al., 2018). This result suggests
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45 that electrical stimulation of the LPBe may be related to the activation of affective
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47 mechanisms rather than goal-directed behaviors (as observed with the LH).
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51 A similar dissociation has been found at other sites such as the thalamus, where
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53 the anterior region of the medial parafascicular subnucleus was positive for ICSS
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55 behavior, while stimulation of its posterior region improved learning by facilitating the
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57 acquisition and retention of two-way active avoidance conditioning (Vale-Martinez et
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3 al, 1999). Likewise, it has been reported that some drugs (e.g., lysergic acid
4 diethylamide [LSD], buspirone, and pentylenetetrazole) can induce place preferences
5 but not self-administration behaviors, whereas others (e.g., pentobarbital or
6 phencyclidine) cannot induce conditioned place preferences but can sustain self-
7 administration behaviors (Bardo and Bevins, 2000).
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14 Preferences for tastes and places associated with electrical stimulation have also
15 been observed in other brain areas anatomically connected to the LPBe, such as the
16 insular cortex (Cubero and Puerto, 2000; García et al., 2013). At the same time, findings
17 in the VTA have revealed neuronal populations with different electrophysiological
18 properties responsible for either reward or aversion, pain or analgesia, escape or self-
19 stimulation according to the precise localization of the electrode (Prado and Roberts,
20 1985; Salamone, 1994; Hikida et al., 2016; Morales and Margolis, 2017).
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30 Stimuli associated with LPBe electrical stimulation were presented in a
31 **concurrent** or contiguous manner in all studies by our group on preference/aversion
32 (Simon et al., 2007, 2008, 2009, 2011, 2013), and these effects disappeared when a time
33 delay was introduced (García et al., 2014). This finding suggests that the acquisition and
34 retention processes might involve a rigid (implicit) learning procedure (García et al.,
35 2014), explaining why animals benefited from an increase in the number of trials
36 (Simon et al., 2013) and why the learning was not acquired when there was a time delay
37 (García et al., 2014).
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49 The effects of LPBe electrical stimulation are consistent with results obtained
50 using natural stimuli (Mediavilla et al., 2000; 2005-for a review-; Yamamoto and Sawa
51 2000a; 2000b; Zafra et al., 2002; 2016). These effects may activate the same circuits as
52 those observed with acute or chronic stress, exposure to emotionally arousing material,
53 or even drug addiction (Schwabe et al., 2010; Darcq and Kiefer, 2018). These have been
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3 proposed to involve activation of a visceral pathway, promoting the generation of
4 stereotyped behaviors and inducing implicit learning (Schwabe et al., 2010).
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6 Conversely, lesions of the LPBe, one of the first central relays in this viscerovagal-
7
8 LPBe pathway, appear to selectively impair implicit learning (Mediavilla et al., 2005).
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12 The well-documented presence of opiate receptors in the LPBe (Mansour et al.,
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14 1995; Chamberlin et al., 1999; Wolinsky et al., 1996) suggests that it not only generates
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16 nutritional preferences/aversions ~~in taste and place conditioning procedures~~ but might
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18 also participate in the processing of substances of abuse (Bechara et al., 1993). Indeed,
19
20 some authors have attributed the LPBe with a key role in processing the discriminative
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22 properties of morphine (Jaeger and Van der Kooy, 1993) and probably the aversive
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24 properties derived from peripheral visceral effects (Bechara et al., 1993; Nader et al.,
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26 1996). However, the LPBe may also be essential for the rewarding properties of drugs
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28 that act on the opiate system (Simon et al., 2007; 2011; Hurtado and Puerto, 2018).
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33 As already noted, our experimental groups learned to associate both places and
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35 flavors with electrical stimulation of the LPBe, but they showed a greater propensity for
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37 spatial cues. This result may be related to the important role for addicted individuals of
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39 the places in which the drugs are taken (Koob & Le Moal, 2000; Koob et al., 2014) and
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41 to the development of dependency and/or tolerance with repeated administrations (See,
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43 2002). In this regard, a tolerance effect has been observed after repeated stimulation of
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45 the LPBe, especially when administered passively (not contingently) by the
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47 experimenter (Hurtado and Puerto, 2016; 2018) These findings are in agreement with
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49 the report by other authors that withdrawal reactions were precipitated by a peripherally
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51 acting opioid antagonist that generated activation throughout the visceral pathway,
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53 specifically in the PBe (Hamlin et al., 2001).
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3 Finally, other studies in our laboratory showed that naloxone blocked the
4 rewarding effects of stimulation in a cCPP procedure when the task was conducted **in a**
5 **new maze** but not when conducted in the same setting as that of the initial learning
6 acquisition (Simon et al., 2007; 2011; García et al. 2014). These findings suggest **again**
7 that opiates present in this parabrachial area may act *via* a circuit that is independent of
8 dopamine (Simon et al., 2007; 2011), which was not the case with LH stimulation
9 (Simon et al., 2011). Furthermore, administration of this opiate antagonist eliminated
10 the hedonic component without affecting the motivation that keeps animals in an
11 expectant state when placed in the same experimental setting (Simon et al., 2007; 2011;
12 García et al. 2014). In a similar way, other studies have shown that naloxone injection
13 eliminated the rewarding reactions but not the motivation of animals that had previously
14 received heroin or cocaine (McFarland and Ettenberg, 1998).

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17 However, the complexity of the processing of drugs of abuse suggests that these
18 systems may induce long-term neuroadaptations and may recruit new systems (Koob
19 and Le Moal, 2000; Hamlin, 2001; Koob et al., 2014). For example, these stimuli may
20 also activate circuits involved in incentive attribution processes, by which animals
21 progressively acquire an improved estimation of the circumstances and actions from
22 retrospective experience and make a motivational/affective reevaluation of these
23 circumstances and/or actions based on prevailing states of the body and brain, as
24 proposed by some authors (Dayan and Berridge, 2014).

25 **8- Interpretation and future guidelines**

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27 Globally, our experiments have shown that electrical stimulation of the LPBe in
28 combination with CTP and cCPP behavioral procedures generates preferences (and
29 aversions) toward stimuli with which it is associated in a contiguous manner. This effect
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3 is totally blocked by naloxone when animals are placed in a new maze (Simon et al.
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5 2007; 2008; 2009; 2011; 2013; 2016; Garcia et al., 2014).
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8 These data may be compatible with some current theories on reward
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10 mechanisms and addiction such as the Opponent Process theory (Solomon and Corbitt,
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12 1974 -cited by Koob et al., 2014-), initially referred to classical substances of abuse but
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14 later to binge eating and other behavioral disorders. According to this theory, a
15
16 ~~continuum from occasional and limited use of substances to a chronically relapsing~~
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18 ~~disorder may be explained by interactions of mechanisms responsible for developing~~
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20 ~~habits/incentive salience with those involved in executive control and affective~~
21
22 ~~regulation~~ mechanisms that support addictive behavior, characterized by compulsive
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24 seeking behavior, loss of control, and a negative emotional state, would be temporarily
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26 connected in an opponent loop containing: an *A-process*, giving rise to unconditional
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28 affective reactions (euphoria) that quickly decay, producing 'tolerance'; and a *B-process*,
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30 emerging immediately after the first process but dependent on a different
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32 neurobiological mechanism, generating an aversive craving state that is amplified with
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34 repeated exposure (Koob and Le Moal, 2000; Moore et al., 2017). This conceptual
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36 framework, subsequently developed by Koob and Le Moal, focuses on motivational-
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38 affective circuits/systems and hypothesizes that transition towards compulsive use and
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40 loss of control is accompanied by chronic perturbations of homeostatic systems
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42 (allostasis) and by neuroadaptations, leading to behavioral sensitization (Koob and Le
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44 Moal, 2000; Koob, et al., 2014). Accordingly, the presence in the brainstem of regions
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46 such as the LPBe, which process opiate-mediated positive (and/or aversive) affective
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48 information (Simon et al., 2007; 2008; 2009; 2011; 2013; García et al., 2014) and where
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50 a tolerance effect has been observed (Hurtado and Puerto, 2016; Hurtado et al., 2016),
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52 suggests that this region may possibly form part of wider hedonic-affective circuits that
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3 may be hierarchically controlled by anterior prosencephalic regions (Roitman et al.,
4 2004; Berridge and Kringelbach, 2015) and whose components require further
5 elucidation.
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10 According to other researchers, desire, pleasure, and the learning of associations
11 are elements that simultaneously intervene in any gratifying experience (due to natural
12 stimuli, stimulation, or drugs) and may be dissociated (Waraczynski, 2006; Berridge
13 and Robinson, 1998; Berridge and Kringelbach, 2015). According to this hypothesis,
14 the neurobiological mechanisms that sustain addiction evolved to support homeostatic
15 behaviors (e.g., food, water intake or sexual behavior) important for individual or
16 species survival (Kelley and Berridge, 2002). Rewards also act as incentives, generating
17 neural representations that not only allow the learning of crucial associations for
18 survival but also govern the search for these rewards (Kelley and Berridge, 2002;
19 Hyman et al., 2006; Darceq and Kieffer, 2018). In this theoretical framework, dopamine-
20 independent opiate-mediated transmission would be part of the circuit involved in the
21 subjective experience of pleasure (*'liking'*), while the mesolimbic dopaminergic pathway
22 would be part of the seeking circuits (*'wanting'*), integrating attention and sensorimotor
23 mechanisms and promoting the formation of 'habits' and the generation of 'compulsive'
24 seeking behaviors (Kelley and Berridge, 2002; Berridge and Kringelbach, 2015). From
25 this perspective, the mesolimbic system and its connections, widely distributed
26 throughout the brain, would sustain motivation, while another smaller circuit would
27 encode the hedonic component, possibly overlapping with pathways involved in
28 processing aversive effects (Kelley and Berridge, 2002; Berridge and Kringelbach,
29 2015). LPBe may be part of this second system that encodes the hedonic/aversive
30 aspects of stimulation.
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58 Publications by Salamone support the idea that dopamine regulates components
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3 other than pleasurable feelings (Salamone and Correa, 2012; Salamone et al., 2016;
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5 2018): They noted that its release not only in positive but also in aversive/stressful
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7 situations suggests that it may be more related to 'motivation', including activational,
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9 attentional, and motor aspects (Salamone and Correa, 2012; Salamone et al., 2016).
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11 They observed that dopaminergic antagonists affect behavioral activation and produce
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13 changes in response allocation, with the selection of lower-cost behavior in both
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15 discriminative learning tasks (T-maze) and operant procedures (lever-pressing or effort-
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17 based selection), (Salamone et al., 1991; 2016). **Conversely, drugs that increase**
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19 **dopaminergic transmission tend to enhance behaviors requiring a high effort (Salamone**
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21 **et al., 2016; Hernández et al., 2010) or low subjective opportunity (Hernandez et al.,**
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23 **2010).** Recording of the dopaminergic signal of the mesolimbic system at different time
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25 scales indicated that this system may integrate information from different motivational
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27 microcircuits, serving as a sensory-motor interface (Salamone & Correa, 2012;
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29 Salamone et al., 2016). Our experimental findings for the LH are consistent with these
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31 data, given that ICSS induced plastic changes in dopaminergic receptors and naloxone,
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33 unlike in the case of the LPBe, was not able to block this effect (Simon et al., 2011;
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35 2016). Further research is warranted on the differential characteristics of the two
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37 systems.
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44 Shizgal et al developed 'neuroeconomical models' of decision making, based on
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46 objective variables that indicate the extent to which an individual, after learning the
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48 association of a behavior with its consequences, participates in seeking behaviors and
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50 reward pursuit rather than alternative behaviors such as resting or grooming, which
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52 could compete with reward acquisition (Solomon et al., 2017). **In this regard, the**
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54 **reward-mountain model predicts that changes in dopamine release can modify the**
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56 **pursuit of brain stimulation reward by rescaling the reward intensity, and this may**
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3 involve a decrease in subjective effort and/or a reduction in the value of alternate
4 activities (Hernandez et al., 2010; 2012). These modifications in dopamine tone do not
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6 appear to correlate well with variables related to affective aspects (Scardocho et al.,
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10 2015).

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12 Our behavioral and neurochemical results obtained in the LPBe and LH support
13 these dissociations: As has already been mentioned, taste/place preferences induced by
14 LPBe electrical stimulation were completely blocked by naloxone (Simon et al., 2007;
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16 2011), whereas preferences for cues associated with LH electrical stimulation were not
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18 (Simon et al., 2011). In addition, ICSS operant behavior was readily obtained with LH
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20 stimulation but not with PBL stimulation (Simon et al., 2011).
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26 The above data on behavioral and neurochemical dissociations support the idea
27 that heterogeneous substrates encoding activational and affective (and perhaps other)
28 aspects of reward may overlap in some brain areas (Roitman et al., 2004; Berridge and
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30 Kringelbach, 2015).
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35 In conclusion, the brainstem LPBe receives peripheral gustatory and visceral
36 information (Fulwiler and Saper, 1984; De Lacalle and Saper, 2000) that is connected to
37 anterior brain areas such as the so-called "extended amygdala" (Li et al., 2006; Gauriau
38 and Bernard, 2002), and it may play an important role in processing affective reward
39 components other than those that involve the mesolimbic system (Kelley and Berridge,
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41 2002). Given that facial expressions consistent with hedonic reactions feelings can be
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43 generated in decerebrated animals at brainstem level (Grill and Norgren, 1978; Castro et
44
45 al., 2015) and opiates are present in the LPBe (Wolinsky et al., 1996; Chamberlin et al.,
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47 1999), the effects of natural rewards, electrical stimulation, and even drugs of abuse
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49 may be neurobiologically related to an affective reward mechanism in this area. The
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51 combination of behavioral and pharmacological procedures with novel techniques such
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3 as optogenetics or other genetic manipulations (e.g., gene activation/silencing,
4 transgenics) can improve our global understanding of this system and advance our
5 knowledge of possible long-term neuroadaptations within and between systems.
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11
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Figure 1: Sagittal section of rat brain depicting some areas known to support Intracranial Self-Stimulation behavior [Adapted from Phillips and Fibiger, 1989].

Figure 2: Quantitative Autoradiography of D1 receptors.

Left: Coronal sections showing significant changes in D1 receptor expression in an animal (13E) from the LH-ICSS group. Right: Schematic representation of areas with significant labeling, from the corresponding section of the atlas of Paxinos and Watson.

Figure 2B (OPTIONAL, EDITORIAL TEAM DECISION): Quantitative Autoradiography of D1 receptors showing D1 receptor expression in an animal (2C) from the Control Group.

Figure 3: Specific ^3H -DAMGO mu-receptor binding in nine coronal rat brain sections in self-stimulated (n=9) and control (n=8) animals. Data were analyzed with a 2-tailed Student's t-test for unrelated samples and expressed as means \pm SEM. LH-ICSS animals showed significantly higher Mu receptor binding in the IP nucleus alone ($t=2.485$ 14 df , $p<0.026^*$) [Reprinted from: Neurobiology of Learning and Memory, 127. Simon et al. Changes in D1 but not D2 dopamine or mu-opioid receptor expression in limbic and

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3 motor structures after lateral hypothalamus electrical stimulation: A quantitative
4 autoradiographic study, page 20 (©2016), with permission from Elsevier].

5
6 Abbreviations:

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8 *Sections:* PFC: prefrontal cortex, NAC: nucleus accumbens, BNST: bed nucleus
9 of the stria terminalis, HC: hippocampus, VTA: ventral tegmental area, CG: central grey
10 area, DR: dorsal rafe, NPB: parabrachial area, LC: locus coeruleus.

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13 *Specific nuclei and subnuclei:* AI: agranular insular cortex; O: orbital cortex; Cg:
14 cingulate cortex; L: limbic cortex; M1A-M1B: primary motor cortex; AcbSh: nucleus
15 accumbens, shell; AcbC: nucleus accumbens, core; CPu1: caudate putamen, matrix;
16 CPu2: caudate putamen, striosomas; BNSTm: bed nucleus of the stria terminalis, medial
17 part; BNSTl: bed nucleus of the stria terminalis, lateral part; LSI: lateral septal nucleus,
18 intermediate part; CA1-3: fields of hippocampus; LHb: lateral habenular nucleus;
19 MDM-T: mediodorsal thalamic nucleus, medial part; MDC-T: mediodorsal thalamic
20 nucleus, central part; MDL-T: mediodorsal thalamic nucleus, lateral part; IML-T:
21 intermediolateral cell column; CM-T: central medial thalamic nucleus; VPL-T: ventral
22 posterolateral thalamic nucleus; VPM-T: ventral posteromedial thalamic nucleus; STh:
23 subthalamic nucleus; ZI: zona incerta; BLA: basolateral amygdaloid nucleus, anterior
24 part; Ce: central amygdaloid nucleus; ACo: anterior cortical amygdaloid nucleus; DM:
25 dorsomedial hypothalamic nucleus; LH: lateral hypothalamic area; VMH: ventromedial
26 hypothalamic nucleus; PVP-T: paraventricular thalamic nucleus, posterior part; SN:
27 substantia nigra; VTA: ventral tegmental area; LPAG: lateral periaqueductal grey;
28 SuG: superficial gray layer of the superior colliculus; InG: intermediate gray layer of
29 the superior colliculus; IP: interpeduncular nucleus; MG: medial geniculate nucleus;
30 DR: dorsal raphe nucleus; MnR: median raphe nucleus; LC: locus coeruleus.

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46 **Figure 4:** Electrical stimulation of the lateral hypothalamus in a concurrent CPP task
47 and effect of the administration de 4.0 and 10.0 mg/Kg of the opiate antagonist
48 naloxone. LH-ES: stimulated group; LH-I: implanted non-stimulated group; LH-C:
49 intact control group [Reprinted from Behavioral Brain Research, 225. Simon et al.,
50 Concurrent stimulation-induced place preference in lateral hypothalamus and
51 parabrachial complex: differential effects of naloxone, page 313 (© 2011), with
52 permission from Elsevier].
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Figure 5: Schematic representation of gastrointestinal input to the brainstem *via* the vagal-parabrachial pathway.

Figure 6: Histological localization of the electrode in LPBe-stimulated animals.

Table 1

Comparison of brain $^3\text{H-SCH-23390}$ (D1R antagonist) and $^3\text{H-YM-09151-2}$ (D2R agonist) between ICSS experimental and control groups, using the Student's t-test for unrelated samples [t =value of t in the Student's test; df =degree of freedom; p =probability of t in a 2-way Student's t-test. Results are expressed as nCi].

Examined sections (abbreviations):

1) **Level of the prefrontal cortex (PFC, +3.20 mm from bregma):** PrL-IL: prelimbic-infralimbic cortex; Cg: cingulate cortex; M2: secondary motor cortex; M1: primary motor cortex; AI: agranular insular cortex; LO: lateral orbital cortex; VO: ventral orbital cortex; DEn: dorsal endopiriform nucleus; AOP: anterior olfactory nucleus, posterior part; AcbSh: accumbens nucleus, shell.

2) **Level of the nucleus accumbens (NAC, +1.70 mm from bregma):** CPu1: caudate putamen, matrix; CPu2: striosomas of the caudate putamen; Cg: cingulate cortex; Motor Cx: motor cortex; AcbSh: accumbens nucleus, shell; AcbC: accumbens nucleus, core; LS: lateral septal nucleus; VP: ventral pallidum; CI: claustrum; DEn: dorsal endopiriform nucleus.

3) **Level of the bed nucleus of the stria terminalis (BNST, -0,30 mm from bregma):** CPu1: caudate putamen, matrix; CPu2: striosomas of the caudate putamen; VP: ventral pallidum, LS: lateral septal nucleus; Tu: olfactory tubercle.

4) **Level of the hippocampus (HC, -2.80 mm from bregma):** CA1-3: fields of hippocampus; Hb: habenular nucleus; CPu: caudate putamen; BLA: basolateral amygdaloid nucleus, anterior part; PRh: perirhinal cortex; DEn: dorsal endopiriform nucleus MGP: medial globus pallidus.

5) **Level of the ventral tegmental area (VTA, -4.80 mm from bregma):** PiRe: pineal recess; Hbc: habenular commissure; CA1 field of the hippocampus; DG: dentate gyrus; PRh: perirhinal cortex; DEn: dorsal endopiriform nucleus; SNR: substantia nigra, reticular part; SNC: substantia nigra, compact part; VTA: ventral tegmental area; V2MM: secondary visual mediomedial cortex.

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3 6) Level of the central gray (CG, -5.80 mm from bregma): SNR: substantia
4 nigra, reticular part; SuG: superficial gray layer of the superior colliculus PRh:
5 perirhinal cortex; DEn: dorsal endopiriform nucleus.
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13 **Figure 3B (OPTIONAL, EDITORIAL TEAM DECISION):**

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15 Brain differences in ³H-SCH-23390 binding (D1R antagonist) between ICSS
16 experimental and control groups, using the Student's t-test for unrelated samples
17 [t=value of t in the Student's test; df=degree of freedom; p=probability of t in a 2-way
18 Student's t-test. Results are expressed as nCi].
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21 Examined sections (abbreviations):

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23 1) Level of the prefrontal cortex (PFC, +3.20 mm from bregma): PrL-IL:
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25 primary motor cortex; AI: agranular insular cortex; LO: lateral orbital cortex; VO:
26 ventral orbital cortex; DEn: dorsal endopiriform nucleus; AOP: anterior olfactory
27 nucleus, posterior part; AcbSh: accumbens nucleus, shell.
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31 2) Level of the nucleus accumbens (NAC, +1.70 mm from bregma): CPu1:
32 caudate putamen, matrix; CPu2: striosomas of the caudate putamen; Cg: cingulate
33 cortex; Motor Cx: motor cortex; AcbSh: accumbens nucleus, shell; AcbC: accumbens
34 nucleus, core; LS: lateral septal nucleus; VP: ventral pallidum; CI: claustrum; DEn:
35 dorsal endopiriform nucleus.
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39 3) Level of the bed nucleus of the stria terminalis (BNST, -0.30 mm from
40 bregma): CPu1: caudate putamen, matrix; CPu2: striosomas of the caudate putamen;
41 VP: ventral pallidum, LS: lateral septal nucleus; Tu: olfactory tubercle.
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45 4) Level of the hippocampus (HC, -2.80 mm from bregma): CA1-3: fields of
46 hippocampus; Hb: habenular nucleus; CPu: caudate putamen; BLA: basolateral
47 amygdaloid nucleus, anterior part; PRh: perirhinal cortex; DEn: dorsal endopiriform
48 nucleus MGP: medial globus pallidus.
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52 5) Level of the ventral tegmental area (VTA, -4.80 mm from bregma): PiRe:
53 pineal recess; Hbc: habenular commissure; CA1 field of the hippocampus; DG: dentate
54 gyrus; PRh: perirhinal cortex; DEn: dorsal endopiriform nucleus; SNR: substantia nigra,
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3 reticular part; SNC: substantia nigra, compact part; VTA: ventral tegmental area;
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5 V2MM: secondary visual mediomedial cortex.

6 6) Level of the central gray (CG, -5.80 mm from bregma): SNR: substantia
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8 nigra, reticular part; SuG: superficial gray layer of the superior colliculus PRh:
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10 perirhinal cortex; DEn: dorsal endopiriform nucleus.
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Figure 2: Quantitative Autoradiography of D1 receptors.
Left: Coronal sections showing significant changes in D1 receptor expression in an animal (13E) from the LH-ICSS group. Right: Schematic representation of areas with significant labeling, from the corresponding section of the atlas of Paxinos and Watson.

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190x254mm (96 x 96 DPI)

Figure 2B: Quantitative Autoradiography of D1 receptors showing D1 receptor expression in an animal (2C) from the Control Group.

Figure 3: Specific³H-DAMGO mu-receptor binding in nine coronal rat brain sections in self-stimulated (n=9) and control (n=8) animals. Data were analyzed with a 2-tailed Student's t-test for unrelated samples and expressed as means \pm SEM. LH-ICSS animals showed significantly higher Mu receptor binding in the IP nucleus alone ($t=2.485$ 14df, $p<0.026^*$). [Reprinted from: Neurobiology of Learning and Memory, 127. Simon et al. Changes in D1 but not D2 dopamine or mu-opioid receptor expression in limbic and motor structures after lateral hypothalamus electrical stimulation: A quantitative autoradiographic study, page 20 (©2016), with permission from Elsevier].

303x188mm (96 x 96 DPI)

Brain differences in 3H-SCH-23390 binding (D1R antagonist) between ICSS experimental and control groups, using the Student's t-test for unrelated samples [t =value of t in the Student's test; df =degree of freedom; p =probability of t in a 2-way Student's t -test. Results are expressed as nCi].

Examined sections (abbreviations):

- 1) Level of the prefrontal cortex (PFC, +3.20 mm. from bregma): PrL-IL: prelimbic-infralimbic cortex; Cg: cingulate cortex; M2: secondary motor cortex; M1: primary motor cortex; AI: agranular insular cortex; LO: lateral orbital cortex; VO: ventral orbital cortex; DEn: dorsal endopiriform nucleus; AOP: anterior olfactory nucleus, posterior part; AcbSh: accumbens nucleus, shell.
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- 3) Level of the bed nucleus of the stria terminalis (BNST, -0,30 mm. from bregma): CPU1: caudate putamen, matrix; CPU2: striosomas of the caudate putamen; VP: ventral pallidum, LS: lateral septal nucleus; Tu: olfactory tubercle.
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- 6) Level of the central gray (CG, -5.80 mm. from bregma): SNR: substantia nigra, reticular part; SuG: superficial gray layer of the superior colliculus PRh: perirhinal cortex; DEn: dorsal endopiriform nucleus.

252x163mm (96 x 96 DPI)

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Figure 4: Electrical stimulation of the lateral hypothalamus in a concurrent CPP task and effect of the administration of 4.0 and 10.0 mg/Kg of the opiate antagonist naloxone. LH-ES: stimulated group; LH-I: implanted non-stimulated group; LH-C: intact control group [Reprinted from Behavioral Brain Research, 225. Simon et al., Concurrent stimulation-induced place preference in lateral hypothalamus and parabrachial complex: differential effects of naloxone, page 313 (© 2011), with permission from Elsevier].

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167x102mm (150 x 150 DPI)

45 Figure 5: Schematic representation of gastrointestinal input to the brainstem via the vagal-parabrachial
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Figure 6: Histological localization of the electrode in LPBe-stimulated animals.

TABLE 1:
D1 and D2 changes in dopamine receptors after self-stimulation of the Lateral Hypothalamus

<i>Region</i>		<i>D1 (t)</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Sig. (bilat)</i>	<i>D2 (t)</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Sig. (bilat)</i>
Prefrontal Cortex (PFC)	DEn	0.698	14	0.497	-2.101↓	14	0.05*
	AcbSh	-2.409 ↓	6	0.05*	--	--	--
N. Accumbens (NAC)	CPu 2	2.429 ↑	15	0.028*	1.649	14	0.121
	AcbSh	2.047	13	0.061	0.967	14	0.350
	VP	4.309 ↑	11	0.001*	1.249	13	0.234
Bed Nu of the S.T.(BNST)	CPu 2	3.622 ↑	5	0.015*	--	--	--
Hippocampus (HC)	CPu	2.264 ↑	15	0.039*	1.520	15	0.149
	MGP	2.403 ↑	11	0.035*	0.189	14	0.853